

The influence of human resource development and motivation on the performance of health workers at Lepo-Lepo health center, Kendari city, southeast Sulawesi province, Indonesia, 2024

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 23(01), 481–488

Publication history: Received on 25 May 2024; revised on 03 July 2024; accepted on 05 July 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.23.1.1928>

Abstract

Background: The importance of HRH development on the performance of healthcare workers is particularly relevant in the current context of the healthcare industry. With advances in medical technology, rapid changes in health policy, and the need for quality health services, this study can make a positive contribution in improving the understanding of how HRD can positively impact the performance of health workers. Several studies have suggested that high motivation can improve productivity, quality care, and patient satisfaction.

Objective: This study aims to determine the effect of human resource development and motivation on the performance of health workers at the lepo-lepo health center in 2024.

Method: This type of research is quantitative research using observational analytic research methods, and using a cross sectional study approach. The population in this study were health workers, namely nurses at the lepo-lepo health center. The sample in this study was 46 samples taken using the homogeneous population method. Data analysis conducted is univariate and bivariate analysis with multiple regression.

Results: The results of this study indicate that there is an influence between positive HR development with a tcount value of $3.525 \geq t$ table 1.967 and a significance value of $0.001 \leq 0.05$, positive intrinsic factor motivation with a tcount value of $3.671 \geq t$ table 1.967 and a significance value of $0.001 \leq 0.05$ and positive extrinsic factor motivation with a tcount value of $-2.932 \geq t$ table 1.967 and a significance value of $0.005 \leq 0.05$ with nurse performance. The conclusion in this study is that there is an influence between HR development, intrinsic factor motivation, and extrinsic factor motivation with the performance of health workers at the lepo-lepo health center.

Conclusion: There is an influence between HR development, intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation with the performance of health workers at the lepo-lepo health center. The combination of effective HR development, strong intrinsic motivation, and appropriate extrinsic motivation will create a productive work environment and high performance at Lepo-Lepo Health Center.

Keywords: HR Development; Intrinsic Motivation; Extrinsic Motivation; Health Worker Performance

1. Introduction

In this era of globalization, the health sector is one of the sectors that continues to grow and experience significant changes. The performance of health workers is a crucial factor in maintaining the quality of health services. In this context, the development of human resources (HR) in the health sector is an important aspect that needs attention. HR

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development involves improving the skills, knowledge and attitudes of health workers in order to face new challenges and improve the quality of health services. (1)

The increasing complexity of diseases, developments in medical technology, and demands for better health services place health workers in the midst of increasingly severe challenges. Moreover, demographic changes, public health policies, and global issues such as pandemics also put additional pressure on the health system. Therefore, continuous human resource development is needed so that health workers can respond to changes and improve their performance. (2)

In reality, health workers are often faced with various challenges that can affect their performance. Some of these include high workload, psychological stress, lack of infrastructure support, and resource management issues. Amidst these challenges, the motivation of health workers is a key factor that can significantly affect their performance. (3)

The importance of HR development to the performance of health workers is particularly relevant in the context of today's healthcare industry. With advances in medical technology, rapid changes in health policy, and the need for quality health services, this study can make a positive contribution in improving the understanding of how HRD can positively impact the performance of health workers. Several studies have suggested that high motivation can improve productivity, quality care, and patient satisfaction. Meanwhile, human resource management literature provides a framework for understanding the elements of motivation that can be applied in the context of health workers. (4)

In the current context of the healthcare industry, where the global pandemic and increasing workloads may result in increased stress on healthcare workers, it is important to identify motivational factors that can maintain and improve their performance. By understanding the influence of motivation on the performance of health workers, health organizations can develop more effective management strategies, improve the retention of health workers, and ultimately, improve the quality of health services provided to the community (Syukron, Hendriani and Maulida, 2022).

This is in line with research related to the relationship between motivation and performance in health workers reported by Masnah (2020) where there is a positive relationship between motivation and the performance of health workers at the Lakessi Health Center, Parepare City. Another study by Susanti (2019) concluded that motivation which is divided into dimensions of responsibility, achievement, work results, development possibilities, salary, work relationships, status, and work procedures has an influence on the performance of employee nurses. (5)

The performance of employees is one of the factors determining the success of an agency in achieving its goals. Increased employee work will bring progress for the company to survive in a competitive stable business environment. Efforts to improve employee performance are the most serious challenge because the success of achieving goals and the survival of the company depends on the quality of human resource performance in it. High employee performance is highly expected by companies and agencies. This is in line with Constitution No. 36 of 2014 considering that health workers have an important role to improve the quality of maximum health services to the community so that the community is able to increase awareness, willingness, and ability to live healthy so that the highest degree of health will be realized as an investment for the development of socially and economically productive human resources and as one of the elements of public welfare as referred to in the Preamble of the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. The more employees who have high performance, the overall productivity will increase. (6)

Based on the regulation of the minister of health number 43 of 2019 concerning puskesmas, the types of health workers available at puskesmas consist of at least doctors, dentists, nurses, midwives, public health promotion and behavioral science workers, environmental health workers, nutritionists, pharmacists and / or pharmaceutical technical personnel, and technologists.

2. Method

The type of research used in this study is quantitative using observational analytical research methods, and using a cross sectional study approach intended to determine the effect of human resource development and motivation on the performance of health workers at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center.

This research was conducted at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, in March 2024. The population in this study were health workers, namely nurses at the Lepo-Lepo Health Center, totaling 46 people. The sampling technique used in this study was a homogeneous population.

3. Result

3.1 Respondent Characteristic

Table 1 Distribution of respondents based on gender, Age, Last education and nursing job

Respondent Characteristic	Number	Percentage
Gender		
Male	10	21.7%
Female	36	78.3%
Total	46	100%
Age		
25-35	31	67.4%
36-45	11	23.9%
46-55	3	6.5%
56-65	1	2.2%
Total	46	100%
Last Education		
S1 - Ners	34	73.9%
S1- Nursing	4	8.7%
D3- Nursing	8	17.4%
Total	46	100
Nursing Job		
UGD	27	58.7%
Inpatient care	10	21.7%
General Clinic	8	17.4%
Laboratory	1	2.2%
Total	150	100

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Based on table 1, out of a total of 100 respondents, the characteristics of respondents based on gender in men were 10 respondents or (21.7%) in female respondents as many as 36 respondents or (78.3%), based on age the majority of respondents had an age between 25-35 years as many as 31 respondents or (67.4%), at the level of education the majority of respondents were S1-Ners, namely 34 respondents or (73.9%) and at the placement of work locations in the emergency room is where most nurses do their work.

3.2 Univariate analysis

Table 2 shows that of the 46 respondents, the majority received high human resource development as many as 27 respondents or 58.7%, high intrinsic factor motivation as many as 28 respondents or 60%, high extrinsic factor motivation as many as 33 respondents or 71.7%. and high performance of health workers as many as 31 respondents or 67.4%.

Table 2 Distribution of respondents based on human resource development, intrinsic factor motivation, extrinsic factor motivation and performance of health workers

Variable	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
HR Development		
High	27	58.7%
Low	19	41.3%
Total	46	100%
Intrinsic Factor Motivation		
High	28	60.9%
Low	18	39.1%
Total	46	100%
Extrinsic Factor Motivation		
High	33	71.7%
Low	13	28.3%
Total	46	100%
Health Worker Performance		
High	31	67.4%
Low	15	32.6%
Total	46	100%

Source: Primary Data, 2023.

3.3 Bivariate Analysis

Bivariate analysis in this study uses multiple linear regression tests to see if there is an influence between the independent variables, namely HR Development, Intrinsic Factor Motivation, Extrinsic Factor Motivation and the dependent variable, namely Health Worker Performance.

Table 3 Result multiple regression analysis

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.692	0.246		2.817	0.007
	HR Development	0.359	0.102	0.377	3.525	0.001
	Intrinsic Factor Motivation	0.382	0.104	0.398	3.671	0.001
	Extrinsic Factor Motivation	-.316	0.108	-.304	-2.932	0.005

Source: Primary Data, 2023.

Based on table 3 of the multiple linear regression analysis results above using the help of the SPSS version 29 computer program, the multiple linear regression equation is obtained as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3$$

$$Y = 0.692 + 0.359 X_1 + 0.382 X_2 + 0.316 X_3$$

The regression equation above can be explained as follows:

- The constant value of 0.692 indicates that if the variables of HR Development, Motivation of Interinsic Factors, Motivation of Exterinsic Factors are equal to zero then the Performance of Health Workers is 0.692
- The HR Development regression coefficient of 0.359 indicates that if HR Development increases by one unit, the Health Worker Performance will increase by 0.359. Unit with the assumption that other things are constant.
- The Interinsic Factor Motivation regression coefficient of 0.382 indicates that if the Interinsic Factor Motivation increases by one unit, the Health Worker Performance will increase by 0.382. Unit with the assumption that other things are constant.
- The Exterinsic Factor Motivation regression coefficient of 0.316 indicates that if the Exterinsic Factor Motivation increases by one unit, the Health Worker Performance will increase by 0.316. Unit assuming other things are constant.

3.4 Simultaneous Test (F Test)

The f test was conducted to determine the effect of independent variables, namely HR Development, Motivation of Interinsic Factors, Motivation of Exterinsic Factors together (simultaneously) on the dependent variable of Health Worker Performance. With $\alpha = 5\%$ (0.05) and $F_{table} = F(k; n-k) = F(10; 329) = 1.86$. The results of the f test through the help of the SPSS version 29 program can be seen in the following table:

Tabel 4 F test result

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5.770	3	1.923	18.622	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.338	42	.103		
	Total	10.109	45			

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Based on the simultaneous test results (f test) from table 4.11 above, it is known that F_{count} is 18.622 with a significance value of 0.00 while the F_{table} value in the distribution table with an error rate of 5% is 1.86. This means that $F_{count} \geq F_{table}$ ($18.622 \geq 1.86$) with a significance value of $0.00 \leq 0.05$. So it can be concluded that the variables X1, X2, X3 have a positive simultaneous influence on variable Y, which means that HR Development, Motivation of Interinsic Factors, Motivation of Exterinsic Factors have a positive simultaneous influence on the Performance of Health Workers.

3.5 Partial Test (t test)

The t test is conducted to determine the effect of each (partial) independent variable, namely product development and price on consumer purchasing decision variables. With $\alpha = 5\%$ (0.05) and $t_{table} = t(\alpha; n-k-1) = t(0.05; 329) = 1.967$. The t test results can be seen in the following table:

Tabel 5 t test result

Coefficients ^a								
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	0.692	0.246		2.817	0.007		
	HR Development	0.359	0.102	0.377	3.525	0.001	0.891	1.122
	Intrinsic Factor Motivation	0.382	0.104	0.398	3.671	0.001	0.869	1.151
	Extrinsic Factor Motivation	-0.316	0.108	-0.304	-2.932	0.005	0.952	1.150

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Testing each variable partially above can be explained as follows:

- HR Development Variable (X1)

The results of testing with SPSS for the HR Development variable (X1) on Health Worker Performance (Y) obtained a tcount value of 3.525 while the ttable value is 1.967. In addition, the significance value is 0.001 less than 0.05. Because the tcount value \geq ttable ($3.525 \geq 1.967$) and the significance value is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.001 \leq 0.05$), then H0 is rejected Ha is accepted that HR Development has a positive and significant effect on Health Worker Performance.

- Interinsic Factor Motivation Variable (X2)

The results of testing with SPSS for the Interinsic Factor Motivation variable (X2) on Health Worker Performance (Y) obtained a tcount value of 3.671 while the ttable value is 1.967. In addition, the significance value is 0.001 less than 0.05. Because the tcount value \geq ttable ($3.671 \geq 1.967$) and the significance value is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.001 \leq 0.05$), H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted that Interinsic Factor Motivation has a positive and significant effect on Health Worker Performance.

- Motivation Variable Exterinsic Factors (X3)

The results of testing with SPSS for the variable Motivation of Exterinsic Factors (X3) on the Performance of Health Workers (Y) obtained a tcount value of -2.932 while the ttable value is 1.967. In addition, the significance value is 0.005 smaller than 0.05. Because the tcount value \geq ttable ($-2.932 \geq 1.967$) and the significance value is smaller than the significance level of 0.05 ($0.005 \leq 0.05$), then H0 is rejected and Ha is accepted Motivation of Exterinsic Factors has a positive and significant effect on the Performance of Health Workers.

Table 6 Results of the Coefficient of Determination (R2)

Model Summary ^b				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.756 ^a	0.571	0.540	0.321

Source: Primary Data, 2023

Based on table 4.20 the results of the calculation of the coefficient of determination (R2) above, the coefficient of determination (R2) value of 0.756a is obtained, meaning that there is a positive relationship between HR Development, Motivation of Interinsic Factors, Motivation of Exterinsic Factors on Health Worker Performance and has a correlation of 75.6%, the remaining 24.4% is influenced by other factors. From these results, the coefficient of determination (R2) value is 0.571, this means that the HR Development variable, Motivation of Interinsic Factors, Motivation of Exterinsic Factors have a joint contribution of 57.1% to the Health Worker Performance variable (Y). While the remaining 42.9% is influenced by other things.

4. Discussion

4.1 Effect of HR Development on Health Worker Performance

Human resource development is the process of preparing individuals to assume different or greater responsibilities in an organization, usually related to increasing their ability or skill to be more proficient and professional so that they can do the job better. human resource development can be done through education and training so as to improve employee performance.(10)

Based on the results of research on human resource development (HRD) has a significant effect on the performance of health workers with a continuous training program that helps health workers update their knowledge of the latest developments in the medical field. This includes new procedures, technologies, and best practices that can be applied in daily work, intensive clinical training ensures that health workers have the practical skills needed to provide high-quality care. In terms of quality of care, better-trained health workers tend to provide better and higher-quality care, improving patient satisfaction and health outcomes. Many studies have shown a positive relationship between HR development and health worker performance. For example:

- Hospital Studies: Research conducted in various hospitals shows that intensive training and career development programs are associated with improved clinical performance and patient satisfaction.

- Health center studies: Studies in several health centers show that health workers who follow continuous training and have a clear career path show improved performance in terms of service effectiveness and patient satisfaction.

4.2 Effect of Interinsic Motivation Factors on Health Worker Performance

In achieving the goals of the health center, it is necessary to have a driving force arising from within each individual such as responsibility, achievement, recognition of others, the work itself, the possibility of development and progress. Nurses need a motivation given by their superiors in order to create high and good work productivity. Motivation is very necessary, because without motivation nurses are not encouraged to produce increased and good productivity.(11)

Based on the results of the study, intrinsic motivation has a significant influence on the performance of health workers. The following is an explanation of how motivation affects the performance of health workers and some of the aspects involved, namely in job satisfaction Intrinsic motivation comes from satisfaction in doing the job itself. Health workers who feel their work is meaningful and makes a positive contribution tend to be more motivated to perform well. Research in various sectors, including healthcare, shows that intrinsic motivation is positively associated with improved employee performance. This study confirms that when employees feel valued, motivated by the work itself, and find meaning in what they do, they will work harder and with higher quality.

4.3 The Effect of Extrinsic Motivation Factors on the Performance of Health Workers

Extrinsic factors are a person's drive for achievement that comes from outside the person, especially from the organization where he works. Poor quality supervision can cause disappointment for nurses. Leaders must understand how to supervise nurses according to their responsibilities. Leaders must have the skills to supervise nurses at work so that they feel comfortable. Therefore, leaders must try to improve themselves by attending training and education.(12)

Based on the results of the study, extrinsic motivation has a significant and positive influence on the performance of health workers Extrinsic motivation such as incentives and rewards can increase job satisfaction. Health workers who feel appreciated are more likely to be satisfied with their work. Extrinsically motivated health workers tend to be more loyal to the organization and have lower turnover rates. Incentives and rewards help retain qualified health workers. Extrinsic motivation encourages health workers to continuously improve themselves and make better and faster decisions in clinical situations, reducing the risk of medical errors. Research in various health institutions shows that extrinsic motivation is positively associated with improved health worker performance. This study confirms that financial and non-financial incentives, rewards, and supportive working conditions play an important role in improving health worker performance.

5. Conclusion

There is a relationship between maternal knowledge and the incidence of stunting in toddlers with a value of $OR=0.275$, which means that mothers who have a low level of knowledge are 3 times more likely to have stunting in toddlers compared to mothers who have a sufficient level of knowledge. There is a relationship between family income and the incidence of stunting in toddlers with a value of $OR=0.490$, which means that low income levels are 5 times more likely than families who have sufficient income levels. There is a relationship between exclusive breastfeeding and the incidence of stunting in toddlers with a value of $OR=0.285$, which means that toddlers who do not receive exclusive breastfeeding are 3 times more likely to suffer from stunting than exclusively breastfed toddlers. There is a relationship between maternal parenting patterns and the incidence of stunting in toddlers with a value of $OR=0.285$, which means that families that have a poor level of maternal parenting have a 5 times greater chance of having children suffering from stunting compared to families that have a good level of maternal parenting. Meanwhile, there is no relationship between a history of infectious disease and the incidence of stunting in toddlers and there is a relationship between maternal parenting patterns and the incidence of stunting in toddlers in the working area of the North Wakorumba Community Health Center, North Buton Regency in 2023. So that the Community Health Center It is necessary to increase the intensity of outreach to increase community knowledge and enthusiasm in managing family nutrition.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors declare that they no conflict of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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